

ANATOMICAL TERMINOLOGY

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Аннотация. Клиническая терминология является основой разговора в сфере здравоохранения. В этой статье рассматривается важность научной терминологии, подчеркивается ее роль в повышении точности, устранении двусмысленности и сохранении точной медицинской статистики. В нем исследуются особенности научного языка, включая его латинские и греческие корни, а также специализированные префиксы и суффиксы. Кроме того, в нем подчеркивается важность коммуникации с лицами, пострадавшими от врача, межпрофессионального сотрудничества, общественной роли врача и фундаментального принципа конфиденциальности лица.

Ключевые слова: Клиническая терминология, Язык здравоохранения, Медицинский разговор, Точность, Латинские и греческие корни, Префиксы и суффиксы, Врач, знакомства, Межпрофессиональное сотрудничество, функция.

Annotatsiya. Klinik terminologiya sog'liqni saqlash sohasidagi suhbatning asosidir. Ushbu maqola ilmiy terminologiyaning ahamiyatini ochib beradi, uning aniqlikni oshirish, noaniqlikni yo'q qilish va aniq tibbiy statistikani yuritishdagi mavqeini tiklaydi. U ilmiy tilning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini, jumladan uning lotin va yunon ildizlarini hamda maxsus prefiks va qo'shimchalarni o'rganadi.

Bundan tashqari, u shifokor tomonidan jabrlangan odam bilan uchrashish, kasbiy hamkorlik, shifokorning jamiyatdagi roli va shifokor tomonidan ta'sirlangan shaxsning maxfiylikni saqlashning asosiy qoidalarini ta'kidlaydi. Sog'liqni saqlashning murakkab panoramasida ilmiy terminologiya samarali muloqotni osonlashtiradigan va oxir-oqibat bemorlarga yordam ko'rsatishni yaxshilaydigan asosiy vosita sifatida paydo bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Klinik terminologiya, Sog'liqni saqlash tili, Tibbiy suhbat, aniqlik, lotin va yunon ildizlari, prefiks va qo'shimchalar, doktor, shaxs bilan tanishish, inter professional hamkorlik, funktsiya.

Abstract. Clinical terminology is the backbone of conversation within the healthcare area. This article delves into the importance of scientific terminology, highlighting its position in enhancing precision, casting off ambiguity, and keeping accurate medical statistics. It explores the particular characteristics of scientific language, inclusive of its Latin and Greek roots and specialized prefixes and suffixes. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of the doctor-affected person dating, inter professional collaboration, the medical doctor's societal role, and the fundamental precept of medical doctor-affected person confidentiality. In the complex panorama of

healthcare, scientific terminology emerges as the linchpin, facilitating efficient communication and in the end enhancing patient care.

Key words: *Clinical terminology, Healthcare language, Medical conversation, Precision, Latin and Greek roots, Prefixes and suffixes, Doctor, person dating, Inter professional collaboration, function.*

Introduction. Anatomical terminology is the language used by anatomists, physicians, and other healthcare professionals to describe the human frame structure. It is substantial to have a strong understanding of anatomical terminology to speak efficaciously in the medical area. This article ambitions to offer a revision of the final lesson in anatomical terminology highlighting the important thing terms and crucial concepts that scholars must understand.

Main Body.

1- Cardiovascular gadget terminology:

The CVS is accountable for transporting blood in the course of the body. Some of the important thing terms associated with the cardiovascular gadget include:

- Heart: the organ that pumps blood during the body
- Artery: a blood vessel that contains blood away from the coronary heart (pulmonary artery is the handiest artery that contains deoxygenated blood)
- Vein: a form of blood vessel that includes blood returned to the heart (pulmonary vein is the most effective vein that carries oxygenated blood)
- Capillary: a small blood vessel that connects arteries and veins

2- Respiratory system terminology:

This system is accountable for breathing and trade of gases between the body and the external surroundings. Some of the widespread phrases of respiratory system encompass:

- Bronchi: the two tubes that department off from the trachea and result in the lungs
- Trachea: the tube that connects the mouth and nostril to the lungs

Diaphragm: The muscle in our body that separates the chest muscles from the stomach and helps us breathe.

- Alveoli: small air sacs in the lungs where gas exchange occurs

3- Nervous System:

The central nervous system regulates and controls all body functions. Some relevant keywords are as follows.

- Peripheral Nervous System: This is the nervous system that connects the central nervous system with the rest of the human body
- Central Nervous System: Brain and spinal cord although it controls most body functions
- Synapse: connection between two neurons that exchange information with each other
- Nerves: Special cells that carry information throughout the human body

4- Glossary of Digestive System:

This system is responsible for digestion which breaks down complex molecules into simpler forms and then extracts nutrients for metabolism. Important steps in this process are given below.

- Esophagus: The fluid that connects the mouth to the stomach
- Stomach: The organ that breaks down food by acids and enzymes
- Small Intestine: Important nutrients are absorbed through this GIT organ
- Colon: This organ absorbs and produces urine

Conclusion. In end, an extremely good know-how of anatomical terminology is very lots critical for powerful communication in clinical discipline. This final lesson terminology revision covers a number of the maximum complicated and critical phrases from the systems of a human frame. This article has supplied an overview of the key phrases and crucial standards relative to the cardiovascular device, apprehensive device, respiratory machine, and digestive machine. A scientific student have to revise those terms thoroughly to make certain they have got proper grip on anatomical terminology.

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